

ENERGY HARVESTING FOR SHOCK MITIGATION IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

D. Pisani¹, W. Dong¹, H. Ryul Jo¹, M. Rauls², C. Kettenbeil², C.S. Lynch^{1*}

¹Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, UCLA, Los Angeles, CA, USA

²Cal Tech, MC 205-45, 1200 E. California Blvd., Pasadena, CA 91125 Pasadena, CA, USA

* Corresponding author (cslynch@seas.ucla.edu)

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1. Introduction

Impact generated stress waves induce large strain components and produce significant damage from failure. This occurs in compression and when the stress waves reflect from free surfaces and produce tension. The subject discussed herein is progress toward the development of an active multifunctional multilayered composite material system capable of modifying its properties in response to impact in a manner that mitigates damage. The approach is to harvest a fraction of the impact generated mechanical energy as electrical energy, transport this electrical energy ahead of the shock front, and use this electrical energy to modify an active material system ahead of the shock prior to shock arrival in a manner that will disperse the shock front, steer the shock away from sensitive areas, or actively manipulate the failure mechanism.

The successful implementation of this strategy will require generation of a large electrical pulse from the initial impact using an active material for shock energy harvesting (the primary material), and inducing a change in the material ahead of the shock with an active material or material system responsive to an electrical pulse (the secondary material). The primary and secondary active materials currently being explored are compositions of lead zirconate titanate (x)PbZrO₃(1-x)PbTiO₃ (PZT), but with markedly different properties. The composition is being varied and dopants are being added to enhance the desired properties for each function. Ideally, the primary active material can be shock depolarized to produce pulsed power independent of the shock propagation direction. This has led to consideration of using the pressure phase transformation from ferroelectric to antiferroelectric in the primary active material. Several approaches are under consideration for the

secondary active material. These include modified compositions of PZT that can be driven through a phase transformation by an electric field, or other compositions that can be transformed from a homogeneous structure to a periodic structure. These responses must occur in the microsecond time frame to be effective.

In the sections that follow the PZT phase diagram is briefly discussed together with the ability of stress and electric field to shift the phase boundaries, the energetics of domain wall motion and phase boundary motion are addressed, the experimentally determined hydrostatic response of 95-5 PZT is presented, experimental results of impact in a split Hopkinson bar are presented, experimental results for potential secondary active materials that undergo an electric field driven antiferroelectric to ferroelectric phase transformation are presented, and a potential material system capable of shifting from a homogeneous to a periodic structure is discussed.

Key results include measurements of material behavior under combined hydrostatic pressure to 1 GPa and electric field loading to 5 MV/m. This is followed by dynamic loading split Hopkinson bar results that indicate that although 95-5 PZT will undergo a phase transformation under hydrostatic load, it is difficult to drive this transformation with a uniaxial stress due to failure under uniaxial compression. This result led to exploring different compositions of PZT with the goal of reducing the threshold for the ferroelectric to antiferroelectric phase transformation.

2. General Description of PZT

PZT is a solid solution of lead zirconate (PZ) and lead titanate (PT). The composition - temperature phase diagram of PZT is shown in Figure 1 [1]. Above the Curie temperature (T_C) all compositions

display a paraelectric cubic phase (P_C). At the left side of the phase diagram, PZ is orthorhombic antiferroelectric (A_O) and displays low temperature and high temperature antiferroelectric structures. At the right side of the phase diagram, PT is ferroelectric with a tetragonal structure (F_T) and a c/a ratio around 1.06.

As the fraction of PT is increased past 5%, the structure changes from A_O to ferroelectric rhombohedral (F_R), and as it passes 48% PT the structure changes from F_R to F_T .

Figure 1. The composition vs. temperature phase diagram of PZT with MPB compositions marked by vertical dashed lines.

The transitions from A_O to F_R and from F_R to F_T are marked with dashed vertical lines in Figure 1. These are morphotropic phase boundaries (MPBs). Compositions near the 95-5 MPB are of particular interest because stress or electric field can cause this boundary to shift. This results in stress and electric field induced phase transformations. Compositions near the 52/48 MPB are also of interest because two phases can coexist near this boundary. This results in enhanced electro-mechanical coupling.

2.1 The Energetics of Stress and Electric Field Driven Phase Transformations

Compositions of PZT under consideration as the primary active material include a 52-48 PZT composition that is near the F_R - F_T morphotropic phase boundary (MPB), and a Nb doped 95-5 PZT near the A_O - F_R MPB. The mechanism for depolarization of 52-48 PZT is primarily ferroelastic domain wall motion. This is a constant volume

process and thus the driving force for domain wall motion comes from the deviatoric component of the stress tensor. The mechanisms for depolarization of 95-5 PZT are domain wall motion within the F_R phase, and a phase transformation from the F_R to A_O phase. The phase transformation involves a volume reduction or around 1%. The driving force for the phase transformation thus comes from the hydrostatic component of the stress tensor. Depolarization by domain wall motion and by F_R - A_O phase transformation are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Deformation is associated deviatoric stress driven domain wall motion in a variant to variant transformation, and with hydrostatic stress driven phase boundary motion in a F_R - A_O phase transformation.

A positive mechanical driving force for domain wall motion and phase boundary motion is present when an increment of work done by external tractions on the material surface is positive during the transformation. A positive work increment is expressed by Equation 1,

$$\int_{\Gamma} t_i \delta u_i d\Gamma > 0 \quad (1)$$

where t_i are the traction components on the surface and δu_i are the displacement increments. Converting from a surface to volume integral leads to Equation (2),

$$\int_V \sigma_{ij} \delta \varepsilon_{ij} dV > 0 \quad (2)$$

where σ_{ij} and $\delta \varepsilon_{ij}$ are the stress and the strain increment.

The stress and the strain increment are separated into hydrostatic and deviatoric components. In the case of domain wall motion, each variant has the same volume but with different strain orientation. The

condition for a positive mechanical driving force for domain wall motion becomes Equation (3),

$$\sigma_{ij}^d \delta \varepsilon_{ij}^d > 0 \quad (3)$$

where the superscript "d" indicates only the deviatoric stress does work on the deviatoric strain change associated with domain wall motion. The condition for a positive mechanical driving force for the F_R - A_O phase transformation becomes Equation (4).

$$\sigma_{kk} \delta \varepsilon_{mm} > 0 \quad (4)$$

where there is a summation implied on the repeated indices. .

There is also an electrical contribution to the driving force for domain wall motion and for the F_R - A_O phase transformation. In this case the external work done on the body is positive if the incremental change of surface charge density in the presence of an electric potential results in positive work (recall the potential, i.e. voltage, is the work per unit charge as the charge moves through the potential). The condition for positive electrical work is stated as Equation (5).

$$\int_{\Gamma} \phi \delta \omega d\Gamma > 0 \quad (5)$$

where ϕ is the potential and $\delta \omega$ is the rate of change of surface charge density. This surface integral is converted to a volume integral and the integrand taken to be positive for a positive driving force, Equation (6)

$$E_m \delta D_m > 0 \quad (6)$$

where E_m are the electric field components and δD_m are the electric displacement increments.

The condition for a positive work rate during either domain wall motion or a phase transformation is that the sum of the mechanical and electrical work must be positive. This is expressed as Equation (7)

$$\sigma_{ij} \delta \varepsilon_{ij} + E_m \delta D_m > 0 \quad (7)$$

The condition of Equation (7) is used to determine whether the driving force is positive when both stress and electric field are present. The terms in

Equation (7) can readily be separated into hydrostatic and deviatoric components to determine the driving force for each depolarization mechanism. For the transformation to take place, the positive driving force must be sufficiently large to overcome an energy barrier to the transformation.

Depolarization by either domain wall motion or by phase transformation can be used to harvest energy. Consider the case where the primary material is open circuited. This holds the electric displacement increment to zero. Application of a positive mechanical driving force for the transformation results in a back electric field that produces a negative electrical driving force for the transformation. This can produce very large electric field levels that can then be harvested as electrical energy.

2.2 The F_R - A_O Pressure Driven Transformation in 95-5 PZT

The A_O phase occupies approximately 1% less volume than the F_R phase. Hydrostatic pressure therefore provides a positive driving force for the F_R to A_O phase transformation. Compositions just on the F_R side of the 95-5 MPB are used to obtain this phase transformation. The F_R phase is stabilized by the addition of small amounts of Nb as described by Berlincourt [2]. Increasing the hydrostatic pressure shifts the 95-5 phase boundary. Figure 3 shows the pressure - temperature phase diagram of 95-5 PZT doped with 2% Nb [3].

Figure 3. The pressure - temperature phase diagram of 95-5 PZT doped with 2% Nb. The dashed lines represent the reverse transformation.

95-5 PZT was fabricated through a solid oxide route, cut to desired shapes, electroded, and poled in the ferroelectric phase by the application of an electric field in excess of the coercive field. Specimens were then placed in a hydrostatic pressure chamber and stress depoled. The resulting electric displacement vs. electric field and strain vs. electric field data are shown in Figure 4. The electric displacement was initially at the remnant polarization value of 0.35 C/m². At a hydrostatic pressure of 350 MPa the material underwent a phase transformation to the non-polar A_O phase. The transformation strain took the material from the remnant strain state of the F_R phase to the zero remnant strain state of the A_O phase.

Figure 4. The electric displacement vs. hydrostatic pressure and the strain vs. hydrostatic pressure behavior of 95-5 PZT as a function of hydrostatic pressure showing the phase transformation.

The strain vs. pressure curve shows strain for the first pressure cycle and the second pressure cycle. In the first cycle the pressure vs. strain curve exhibited an elastic perfectly plastic like behavior. In the second cycle the material softened and then stiffened. Other experimental results not shown here indicate that this may be due to the pressure depoled material being a mixture of F_R and A_O phases. This

is consistent with the depoled material having many residual nucleation sites for the phase transformation.

The hydrostatic stress driven phase transformation in 95-5 PZT can be used to harvest electrical energy from a shock wave. A bulk compression wave carries a stress in the shock propagation direction given by Equation (8)

$$\sigma_{xx} = \rho U_s U_p \quad (8)$$

where ρ is the material density and U_s and U_p are the shock velocity and particle velocity respectively. In the elastic regime, stress perpendicular to this direction is given by Equation (9),

$$\sigma_{yy} = \sigma_{zz} = \frac{\nu}{1-\nu} \sigma_{xx} \quad (9)$$

where ν is Poisson's ratio.

In the case of the F_R-A_O phase transformation the hydrostatic component of stress produces a positive driving force for the phase transformation and resulting depolarization regardless of the direction of compression wave propagation relative to the polarization direction. This offers an advantage over the shock depolarization of 52-48 PZT where the domain wall motion is driven by the difference between the compressive stress component in the polarization direction and the stress components perpendicular to the polarization direction. In either case the stress driven depolarization can be used to harvest energy from the shock.

2.3 Preliminary Hopkinson Bar Results for 95-5 and 52-48 PZT

A Hopkinson bar was used to produce a uniaxial stress wave in specimens of 95-5 PZT and 52/48 PZT. The Hopkinson bar loading system consists of a specimen placed between two long rods. A third rod is launched into the pair. This results in a uniaxial stress wave traveling down the first rod, through the specimen, and into the second rod. Strain gages on each rod are used to determine the stress in each rod. The strain-time and stress-time histories in each rod are used to back out the stress-strain behavior of the specimen.

In these preliminary experiments, the difference between open circuit and short circuit response of the materials was sought. The results of the open circuit tests was a large electrical pulse that obscured the strain gage data. Shorting the electrodes was found to be insufficient to prevent this electrical pulse from obscuring the strain data, so an aluminum foil was folded over the specimens to create a Faraday cage around the specimen. This resulted in the successful measurement of a stress-strain curve for the 52-48 and the 95-5 PZT under dynamic loading.

The 52-48 open circuit stress-time curve rises rapidly for about 10 microseconds and then flattens out. A time integration over this rise indicates a strain of about 4,500 microstrain. This corresponds to the anticipated elastic strain obtained by multiplying the 450 MPa stress by the Young's modulus of 100 GPa. The flatter portion of the strain rate vs. time curve cannot be entirely attributed to depolarization. Only about 2000 microstrain would be anticipated from domain wall motion. It is more likely that the flatter portion of the strain-rate vs. time curve corresponds to crushing of porosity and other material damage. The short circuit results utilized a lower amplitude stress pulse. The strain-rate in this case is almost double that of the open circuit specimen. This is likely due to the added contribution of ferroelastic strain associated with domain wall motion. This doubling of the strain-rate over the same time period, and the corresponding doubling of the strain indicates that the effective Young's modulus can be shifted by a factor of two by controlling the electrical boundary conditions.

Figure 5. Dynamic stress-strain and stress-strain rate curves for open circuited and short circuited 52-48 PZT. Note the scale differences. The time duration shown is 40 microseconds.

The results for the 95-5 PZT under dynamic loading were inconclusive. The results displayed non-linear behavior, but the material did not appear to undergo a phase transformation. It appears that the material was failing under uniaxial stress at a level below that required to drive the phase transformation.

2.4 The AF-F Electrically Driven Transformation

Modification of the material ahead of the shock in a manner that mitigates the incoming shock presents a significant challenge. Different approaches using active materials are under consideration. These include inducing periodic anisotropy into a layered composite ferroelectric structure through creating alternate open and short circuited layers, or driving an AF to F phase transformation in the secondary active material that produces a shock that will interact with the incoming shock. The experimental work presented on the secondary active materials includes a set of measurements on the materials that were examined and a description of the fabrication and testing of PZT compositions that can be electrically driven from the A_O phase to the F_R phase with a resulting volume increase.

Compositional modifications under consideration include doping with La, Ba or adding Sn to control the A_O - F_R transformation. For the secondary active material to perform the desired function, it must change its properties within several microseconds of being subjected to an electrical pulse. Several of the compositions under consideration undergo phase transformations from A_O to F_R in response to an electrical pulse.

The results presented describe the effects of composition and dopants on the A_O - F_R electric field driven phase transformations. Compositions on the A_O side of the MPB were modified with the addition of small amounts of Sn, La, and Ba. This affects the electric field threshold for the transformation and the strain change associated with the transformation. The antiferroelectric phase is not polar, thus an electric field provides a positive driving force for the A_O to the F_R phase change. Figure 6 shows the effect of increasing Sn in 2% La - x PZ - y PT - (1-x-y) Sn. The addition of Sn shift the coercive field for the phase transformation.

Figure 6. Double loop response of the A_O to F_R electric field driven phase transformation modified by the addition of Sn and La .

3. Structural modifications in the secondary material

3.1 Induced Periodic Structures

Wave propagation in periodic structures results in multiple reflections at interfaces due to shock impedance mismatch (jumps in the product of density with shock velocity). The linear elastic modulus of ferroelectric materials changes significantly with electrical boundary conditions (open circuit vs. short circuit). The Hopkinson bar results indicate that this is observed under impact loading. This effect is enhanced by the non-linear behavior associated with phase transformation.

The electrical boundary conditions can be changed in the microsecond time frame by blowing a small fuse or activating a small switch and are thus controllable in the time period between initial impact and shock transmission further into the structure. The concept is shown schematically in Figure 7 where the material is initially homogeneous and can be rapidly changed to a periodic structure.

Figure 7. This sketch shows illustrates the concept of switching the microstructure from a homogeneous structure to a periodic structure using an electrical pulse.

3.2 Electric Field Pulse Induced Stress Waves

Another approach under consideration is to use the secondary active material to produce stress waves. Pulsing of the Sn doped A_O composition drives it through the A_O - F_R phase transformation that increases the volume by 1%. The electrical pulse can take place in a microsecond or less. This will give rise to a dilatational stress pulse. Work on phase transforming materials and their temporal response to large electric pulses is ongoing.

4. Concluding remarks

This paper presented an overview of work that is underway on developing new shock mitigation strategies. The approach is to use pulse power generation from the initial impact, feed the pulse power ahead of the shock front, and modify the material in a manner that will help to mitigate damage from the shock. Results were presented for two candidate primary materials to be used for pulse power generation and for potential secondary materials that can respond to the electrical pulse in the microsecond time frame.

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6. References

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